

IMPACT OF QUALITY AND SECURITY MANAGEMENT ON HUMAN CAPITAL BUILDING**Kiguradze H.***PhD student, Business School,
Georgian American University, Tbilisi, Georgia***ABSTRACT**

Creating an employee pool is a critical task for any organization, and it involves attracting and retaining high-quality employees who are committed to the success of the organization. By focusing on creating a positive work environment, providing opportunities for career development, and prioritizing the health and well-being of their employees, organizations can attract and retain the best employees. This leads to a stable and dedicated employee pool that is committed to the success of the organization. This is an essential task for any organization, and it involves attracting and retaining high-quality employees who are committed to the success of the organization. The process of creating an employee pool can be challenging, but there are several steps that organizations can take to attract and retain the best employees.

The article below discusses the importance of TQM and HSE management involvement in creating employee pool and the importance of these two in creating company image.

Keywords: HSSE, TQM, Employee, Employee Pool.

Creating an employee pool involves several steps such as creating a detailed job description that outlines the responsibilities, qualifications, and experience required for the position, promoting the position through various channels to help identify potential candidates who are a good fit for the organization and who share the same values and goals.

Organizations should also provide regular feedback and recognition to their employees. This can help to build a sense of accomplishment and satisfaction among employees and can help to improve performance and productivity.

In addition, organizations should prioritize the health and well-being of their employees. This may involve providing health and wellness programs, offering flexible work arrangements, and creating a safe and supportive work environment.

TQM focuses on continuous improvement and customer satisfaction. By implementing TQM, companies can improve their products and services, streamline their processes, and reduce waste and inefficiency. This can help to build a reputation for quality and reliability, which can improve customer satisfaction and loyalty.

In addition, TQM can help to improve employee satisfaction and engagement. By involving employees in the improvement process and empowering them to take ownership of their work, TQM can create a positive work environment and foster a culture of excellence. This can lead to lower turnover rates and higher employee satisfaction, which can help to attract and retain high-quality employees.

HSE management, on the other hand, focuses on ensuring the safety and well-being of employees and the environment. By implementing HSE management, companies can demonstrate their commitment to safety and sustainability, which can improve their reputation and brand image.

In addition, HSE management can help to reduce accidents and injuries in the workplace, which can improve employee morale and productivity. This can also

help to reduce costs associated with accidents and injuries, which can improve the company's financial performance and profitability.

Furthermore, companies that prioritize HSE management can build a positive reputation with customers and stakeholders who are concerned about environmental and social issues. This can improve customer loyalty and brand reputation, and can also help to attract socially responsible investors and partners.

Total Quality Management (TQM) and Health, Safety and Environment (HSE) management are critical aspects of creating an employee pool that is dedicated to excellence and sustainability. These management systems have a significant impact on the culture of an organization, and they play a crucial role in attracting and retaining high-quality employees.

TQM is a management approach that focuses on continuous improvement and customer satisfaction. It involves all employees in the organization and emphasizes the need for quality in all processes and operations. TQM helps to create a culture of excellence in the workplace, where employees are encouraged to strive for continuous improvement and take ownership of their work.

The impact of TQM on creating an employee pool is significant. TQM helps to attract and retain high-quality employees who are committed to excellence and are passionate about their work. Employees who work in a TQM environment are empowered to take ownership of their work and contribute to the success of the organization. This leads to a culture of continuous improvement, where employees are always looking for ways to improve processes and operations.

HSE management, on the other hand, focuses on ensuring that the workplace is safe and healthy for employees. It involves identifying and managing risks, providing adequate training and resources, and creating a culture of safety in the workplace. HSE management helps to create a workplace where employees feel safe and valued, and where their health and well-being are prioritized.

The impact of HSE management on creating an employee pool is also significant. HSE management

helps to attract and retain high-quality employees who are concerned about their health and safety. Employees who work in a safe and healthy environment are more productive, engaged, and committed to their work. They are also more likely to stay with the organization for the long term, which helps to create a stable and dedicated employee pool.

TQM and HSE management are closely related, and organizations that implement both systems are more likely to create a strong and dedicated employee pool. By focusing on quality, continuous improvement, and safety, organizations can create a workplace culture that is focused on excellence and sustainability. This culture attracts and retains high-quality employees who are committed to the success of the organization.

TQM and HSE management have a significant impact on creating an employee pool that is dedicated to excellence and sustainability. By focusing on quality, continuous improvement, and safety, organizations can create a workplace culture that attracts and retains high-quality employees. This leads to a stable and dedicated employee pool that is committed to the success of the organization. As such, organizations that prioritize TQM and HSE management are more likely to succeed in the long term and create a positive impact on their employees and society.

Total Quality Management (TQM) and Health, Safety, and Environment (HSE) management are two critical management systems that can have a significant impact on a company's image. Both systems focus on creating a culture of excellence, safety, and sustainability within an organization, which can help to build a positive reputation and brand image.

In conclusion, TQM and HSE management can have a significant impact on a company's image and reputation. By implementing these management systems, companies can demonstrate their commitment to quality, safety, and sustainability, which can improve customer loyalty, attract and retain high-quality employees, and build a positive brand image. Therefore,

organizations that prioritize TQM and HSE management are more likely to succeed in the long run and create a positive impact on their employees, customers, and society.

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